

INDICATORS OF THE “ME” CONCEPT

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Abstract: The article provides information about the definition, interpretation, history of its development and its indicators of the concept of “I”. The structure of the concept of “I” is also presented.

Keywords: “I” – concept, humanistic approach, institution.

According to scientists, the image of “I” in a person is formed in the process of self-awareness and self-evaluation in relations with the environment. In studying this problem, many pedagogical and psychological scientists work based on the teachings of the history of the development of human consciousness and the socialization of the individual. Scientists consider the state of formation of the image of “I” as a product and an important aspect of the self-awareness of the individual. Such phenomena as self-assessment-self-awareness are based on social nature and criteria.

Self-concept is a developing system of a person's ideas about himself, which includes: a) perception of his physical, intellectual, characterological, social and other characteristics; b) self-evaluation; c) subjective perception of external factors influencing the personality. The concept of the “self” concept appeared in the 1950s within the phenomenological and humanistic psychology directions. According to (A. Maslow, K. Rogers), biochemists and Freudians, they sought to consider the “self” of a person as a general factor of his morality and development. Symbolic interactionism (C. Cooley, D. Mead) and the concept of identification (E. Erikson) had a significant influence on the formation of the “self” concept. However, the first theoretical developments in this direction were carried out by W. James. He was the first to divide the global “I” of a person into the interconnected “I-creator” (I) and “I-object” (Me).

The concept of “I” is a generalized idea of a person about himself, a system of order of a person in relation to himself, or, as psychologists say, the theory of the “I” concept about itself. It is important to note that the concept of “I” is not a static, but a dynamic psychological phenomenon. The formation, development and change of the concept of “I” are associated with internal and external factors of order. The social environment, including the family and school, influences the formation of the concept of “I” in the process of socialization. This influence is not only at the initial stage of the socialization of the person, but also at a time when the family is the only or absolutely strong social environment of the child, but also does not lose its significance in his life later. With age, the importance of social experience, the numerous formal and informal groups into which the individual is a part, in the development of the concept of “I” increases.

The formation of the personality is associated with the development of a meaningful and constructive “I”. Knowledge of one's own personality is considered in the literature as knowledge of the individual's identity and uniqueness.

The concept of self-awareness means a theoretical picture of oneself (A. A. Rean); a form of a person's experience of his own personality (D. A. Leontiev); a system of self-awareness associated with self-esteem; a system of self-attitude (R. Bernet), etc. Many research materials show that the holistic development of a person is possible only in the presence of positive Self-concepts. The concept of positive self-concept is the sum of all the positive ideas a child has about himself, including positive self-esteem and behavioral tendencies. For a positive self-concept, it is important to recognize both positive and negative qualities, to accept oneself as such, and to have a desire to change oneself.[2]

One of the most advanced theories of the gradual development of the "self-concept" was proposed by the American psychologist Gordon Allport. These stages include the psychological needs of the individual to form a unique personality and the social factors that play a role in this development. 5 of these 8 stages occur in the life of children of primary and preschool age. Stage 1 is the feeling of one's own body. The baby does not perceive himself as a separate person, begins to separate himself from other things. Therefore, he does not distinguish between "mine" and "not mine". However, in the first year of life, babies begin to perceive many sensations emanating from the internal sense organs. Stage 2 is the feeling of self-awareness, that is, the child knows himself as a certain and most important person. This is because the most important starting point for ensuring the integrity and continuity of the "I" is the child's own name. By the age of 2-3, a child who has learned his name begins to understand that he remains the same person, despite all the changes that occur in his development and in his relationships with the outside world. Stage 3 - (3-4 years) the formation of self-esteem. First of all, the feeling of self-esteem is manifested as a feeling of pride that the child experiences when he does something himself. Self-esteem depends on the child's successful completion of the task. Stage 4 - expanding his boundaries. At the age of 4-5, the child begins to understand that he owns not only his physical body, but also important elements of the world around him, including people. At this stage, children begin to master the understanding of the meaning of "I". At the age of 5 (5-6 years), the image of "I" begins to form. At this stage, the child begins to learn how to relate to the people around him, his parents, relatives, and other people, and what they expect from him, how they want him to be. By this time, the child begins to understand the difference between "good" and "bad". Stage 6 (6-12 years old) is conscious, rational self-control. This period of self-formation manifests itself in strong conformity, moral and social obedience. At stage 7, during adolescence, the concept of "I", a sense of integral "I" takes place. The eighth stage of the development of the "I-concept" is associated with the formation of such abilities as self-knowledge and self-esteem. Based on the above considerations, we can say that external environmental factors play a great role in the formation of a person as a person. However, at the same time, it is appropriate to take into account the heredity and individual development and personal potential of the growing child. If we look at the stages of development, we can see that the initial concepts of "I" are formed in the family. In the later stages, this is strengthened. This is related to educational institutions, especially preschool education is of particular importance..

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